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ConcePTION

WP3 – Determination of drug transfer and infant drug exposure during lactation: generation of quantitative and translatable data

D3.6 Generic PBPK* template for predicting drug concentration-time profiles in human breast milk

* *PBPK = physiologically-based pharmacokinetics*

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Abstract

Introduction: Women commonly need medicines during pregnancy and lactation. Currently, there is a knowledge gap about the concentrations of maternal medication reaching human breastmilk. Work package 3 of ConcePTION aims to generate a non-clinical testing platform to determine the concentration-time profiles of medicines in human milk.

Aim: The aim of this deliverable was to explore Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelling as a promising computational tool to predict the concentration-time profiles of medicines in human milk, along with subsequent infant “doses” of these medicines via breastfeeding.

Methods: The PBPK models were developed: (i) in Simcyp v. 21 (Certara) for amoxicillin, valproic acid and caffeine, and in PK-Sim/MoBi v.9.1 (Open Systems Pharmacology) for amoxicillin, valproic acid, caffeine, cetirizine, levetiracetam, metformin, nevirapine, sertraline, tenofovir, zidovudine. First, compound-specific PBPK models for adult human reference subjects were developed and the predictive performance was evaluated. Next, the PBPK models were extended to include the lactation physiology. The concentration-time profiles in plasma and human milk were simulated in a “3 months postpartum”-population. The milk-to-plasma (M/P) ratio was calculated based on the predicted AUC in plasma and milk. Finally, the daily dose (daily infant dosage, DID) received by the infant via human milk, as well as the relative infant dose (RID), were calculated based on both the average and the maximum simulated human milk concentrations.

Results: The reference PBPK models were able to adequately describe the pharmacokinetic profiles of the model medicines included in this study. The lactation PBPK models resulted in an adequate prediction for 7 of the model medicines, while an overprediction of the milk concentrations was found for 3 model medicines. From a safety perspective, it is relevant to note that none of the models resulted in an underprediction of observed milk concentrations. Both software platforms (Simcyp and PK-Sim/MoBi) resulted in similar predictions.

Conclusion: The present study resulted in a generic workflow for the development, evaluation and application of medicine-specific lactation PBPK models. The results obtained with 10 model medicines illustrate that such lactation PBPK models allow simulation of concentration-time profiles of medicines in maternal plasma and milk. In addition, based on model-based simulations, daily infant dosage (and relative infant dose) via breastfeeding can be calculated as well. A particular strength of this approach is that unique quantitative information on infant exposure to medicines via breast milk can be generated in an early (drug development) stage, i.e. before clinical data becomes available. At the same time, application of this workflow to medicines for which clinical (lactation) data are already available will build further confidence in the robustness of this computational approach. Further refinement (e.g. implementation of *in vitro* data reflecting passage of the blood/milk barrier) as well as application to an increasing number of medicines as well as other therapeutic modalities (e.g. biologics), will likely result in improvements of the predictive performance along with broader application potential.

Impact: The generic lactation PBPK framework established here represents an important step towards evidence-based safety assessment of maternal medication in breastfed infants.

Glossary

AUC	Area Under the Curve
$C_{ave, milk}$	Average concentration in human milk
$C_{max, milk}$	Maximum (~ peak) concentration in human milk
CL_{re}	Reuptake clearance (i.e. from milk to blood)
CL_{sec}	Secretion clearance (i.e. from blood to milk)
DID	Daily Infant Dosage
$f_{u_{milk, total}}$	Free fraction in ‘whole’ human milk, i.e. taking protein and lipid binding into account
f_{u_p}	Unbound fraction in plasma
$f_{u_{skimmed\ milk}}$	Free fraction in skimmed milk or ultrafiltrate, taking (only) protein binding (but not lipid binding) into account
HBD	Hydrogen Bond Donors
$LogD_{7.2}$	Logarithm of the partition coefficient between an octanol phase and an aqueous (buffer) phase at pH 7.2
$LogD_{7.4}$	Logarithm of the partition coefficient between an octanol phase and an aqueous (buffer) phase at pH 7.4
LogP	Logarithm of the partition coefficient between an octanol phase and (unbuffered) water as aqueous phase. This is the default parameter to express lipophilicity of a substance.
$LogP_{milk}$	Logarithm of the partition coefficient between milk lipid and (aqueous) ultrafiltrate, taking lipid binding into account
M/P ratio	Milk-to-Plasma ratio
MW	Molecular Weight (Da)
PBPK	Physiologically based pharmacokinetic [modelling]
PSA	Polar Surface Area
Q	Blood flow rate
RID	Relative Infant Dose

1. Introduction

In April 2019, ConcePTION was launched. ConcePTION is a private public partnership that aims to generate information about the use of medicines during pregnancy and breastfeeding: “Building an ecosystem for better monitoring and communicating of medication safety in pregnancy and breastfeeding: validated and regulatory endorsed workflows for fast, optimized evidence generation.” Work Package 3 (WP3) of ConcePTION aims to generate a non-clinical testing platform to determine medicine transfer into the human milk, and subsequent exposure of neonates/infants. While this platform relies on non-clinical methodologies (i.e. *in vivo* animal, *in vitro*, *in silico*), the predicted outcomes are of clinical relevance (e.g. concentration time profiles of medicines in maternal blood and milk).

This deliverable described in the present report reports on the development, evaluation and application of a generic Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic modelling (PBPK) template:

- to predict medicine concentration time profiles in human milk;
- to calculate milk-associated medicine doses ingested by neonates and infants.

2. Methods

Several diseases require either periodic (e.g., infections) or chronic pharmacotherapy (e.g., depression, epilepsy...) during the lactation period. During the development of new medicines, generation of information regarding safe use during lactation is relevant for labelling. PBPK models are a promising tool for prediction of human milk concentrations, and subsequent infant exposure to maternal medication.

This is because PBPK can be used for bottom-up predictions (with or without additional *in vitro* data), i.e., in the absence of any measured (*in vivo*) concentrations in the “target species”. That said, PBPK models are commonly enhanced via so-called middle-out approaches. These imply utilization of (typically sparse) data from lactating females and breastfed children, thereby enabling parameter identification (or estimation; PE) via a fitting procedure. In such a PE procedure, the values of selected PBPK parameters displaying uncertainty can be estimated by using clinical data as input.

For the purpose of this project, the PBPK models were developed in two different and well-known PBPK modelling platforms: (i) the open-source platform Open Systems Pharmacology, which consists of PK-Sim v9.1 and MoBi, and (ii) the Simcyp simulator version 21 (Simcyp Ltd, Sheffield, UK, a Certara company). In the present report, besides the general approaches that were followed, platform-specific details are also provided. Observed data for all model medicines were taken from literature. When the time of the sample with respect to the last dose was not mentioned, samples were assumed to be trough samples.

The general workflow followed for building the lactation PBPK models is described in Figure 1.

Figure 1 General workflow that was used in the present project to develop and evaluate the lactation PBPK models

2.1 Reference PBPK model

The first step was to construct a PBPK model for a reference individual (adult healthy volunteer or patient). Medicine-related parameters (e.g., physicochemical properties) were combined with physiology-related parameters to predict the pharmacokinetic profile of a medicine in “non-lactating” adult populations. A first set of observed data in healthy volunteers and/or patients (i.e. a training dataset) was used to build the model. If necessary, parameters were estimated to fit the observed data, implying the so-called middle-out approach. The predictive performance of the model was then evaluated with a second dataset (evaluation dataset). The generally applied acceptance criterium was less than 2-fold misprediction. However, it should be noted that a 2-fold misprediction is to be considered a worst case scenario. Case-by-case judgement (e.g., misprediction of a single concentration time point in the terminal elimination phase is much less critical than misprediction of the AUC for the full profile) should be used for data interpretation and acceptance/rejection of the predictions. An excellent tutorial about the underlying principles and generic procedures for evaluating the predictive performance of PBPK models has been published by Kuepfer *et al.* (2016) [1].

2.2 Lactation PBPK model

The next step was to extend the PBPK models to reflect the physiology of the “lactating state”. In order to take a standardized approach, and for reasons of feasibility, it was decided to develop and evaluate lactation PBPK models for subjects at three months postpartum. It should however be noted that the same workflow can be applied for other postpartum time points. A compartment representing the lactating breasts was added to the PBPK model structure. Breastmilk was represented as a subcompartment of the breasts.

Two different mechanistic concepts were considered to parametrize the transfer of medicines into human milk:

A first type of model (i.e. the so-called perfusion-limited model) assumed that there is a rapid equilibrium

between plasma and milk. This implies that the concentration of a medicine in human milk can be calculated based on the plasma concentration and the milk-to-plasma ratio (M/P ratio). The M/P ratio can be calculated based on physicochemical properties of a medicine (e.g., pH partitioning, protein binding and distribution into milk lipid), assuming that only the unbound and unionized molecular species will cross the blood-milk barrier. An example of this method is the phase distribution model developed by Fleishaker *et al.* (1987) and Atkinson & Begg, (1990) [2], [3].

Alternatively, the transfer into human milk is assumed to be permeability-limited, which means that the local transfer rate (~biological barrier permeability) of the medicine is the rate-limiting step in the overall secretion process. For some medicines, this may imply the involvement of transporters or carrier proteins at the blood/milk barrier.

As very limited information is available regarding the extent and rate of passage of medicines across the blood/milk barrier, it was decided to rely on the empirical approach proposed by Koshimichi *et al.* [4], allowing to predict *in vivo* M/P ratios based on physicochemical properties of a compound (medicine). Hence, in the lactation PBPK models, the transfer of medicines to human milk and reuptake from human milk were parametrized by the secretion (CL_{sec}) and reuptake (CL_{re}) clearance as defined by Koshimichi *et al.* (2011), respectively. CL_{sec} (Equation 1) is calculated based on the polar surface area (PSA), molecular weight (MW) and the octanol water partition coefficient (LogP) and octanol:buffer(pH 7.4) distribution coefficient (LogD_{7.4}). CL_{re} (Equation 2) is calculated based on LogP and the hydrogen bond donors (HBD).

$$\text{Log}(CL_{sec}) = -3.912 - 0.015 * \text{PSA} + 3.367 * \text{Log}(MW) - 0.164 * \text{Log}\left(\frac{P}{D_{7.4}}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Log}(CL_{re}) = 2.793 + 0.179 * \text{Log}P - 0.132 * \text{HBD} \quad (2)$$

The empirical approach according to Koshimichi also requires knowledge of the unbound fractions of the medicines in plasma and milk. The equations described by Atkinson and Begg (1990) were used to calculate the ('total') free fraction of the medicines in 'whole' human milk ($f_{u_{milk,total}}$, Equation 3). This equation is based on the unbound fraction in skimmed milk ($f_{u_{skimmed\ milk}}$, Equation 4) or the binding to milk protein, and the partition coefficient between milk lipid and ultrafiltrate (P_{milk} , Equation 5). The $f_{u_{skimmed\ milk}}$ is based on the relationship between plasma protein binding and milk protein binding. P_{milk} was calculated from the octanol:buffer(pH7.4) distribution coefficient [3].

$$f_{u_{milk,total}} = \frac{1}{\frac{0.955}{f_{u_{skimmed\ milk}} + 0.045 * P_{milk}}} \quad (3)$$

$$f_{u_{skimmed\ milk}} = \frac{f_{u_{plasma}}^{0.448}}{(6.94 * 10^{-4})^{0.448} + f_{u_{plasma}}^{0.448}} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Log}P_{milk} = -0.88 + 1.29 * \text{Log}D_{7.2} \quad (5)$$

Simulations based on the lactation PBPK models were performed for a population (n = 1000) of lactating subjects, 3 months postpartum. The plasma and human milk concentration-time profiles were predicted. In addition, the milk-to-plasma (M/P) ratio (Equation 6) was calculated based on the predicted area-under-the-curve (AUC) values in plasma and milk.

$$M/P\ ratio = \frac{AUC_{human\ milk}}{AUC_{plasma}} \quad (6)$$

Importantly, the data for lactation is often missing information about the dose or time after last dosing. Therefore, it is recommended to evaluate the predictive performance case-by-case, in view of the availability and/or quality of the data. The evaluation of the predictive performance was mainly based on visual inspection, and whether the observed data were within the 5-95th percentile of the population prediction.

2.2.1. Lactation PBPK models in Simcyp

The Simcyp simulator features a built-in lactation module. A data collection on milk properties and physiology was performed and used for the development of the lactation module within this software platform [5]. The module provides two different approaches as described below:

A. Permeability-limited model

The permeability-limited model implemented in Simcyp is a three-compartment model, existing of extracellular, intracellular and milk compartments. Since the passage of medicines to human milk can be explained by passive diffusion for some compounds, while transporter kinetics are applicable for other medicines [5], this permeability-limited model can account for these various mechanisms. For passive permeability, the model includes options to allow total unbound or only unbound unionized molecules to permeate through the blood-milk barrier.

In order to adequately map the two compartments (plasma-milk) in the permeability model as described by Koshimichi et al. (see above) within the 3-compartment structure of the Simcyp lactation module, some parameters were fixed to (very) high values. To achieve this mapping, values for the passive diffusion clearance, CL_{PD} (maternal blood-breast milk) were fixed to 10^5 L/h (Figure 2).

Values for secretion and reuptake clearance (CL_{re} and CL_{sec} , respectively) were calculated using R for Windows (v. 4.2.2) and Rstudio (v.2002.07.2+576) according to the equations in Koshimichi *et al.* (2011) (Equation 1-2).

Figure 2 Modified structure of the permeability-limited model that was used to describe passage of medicines across the blood-milk barrier as part of the lactation PBPK model structure in the Simcyp simulator.

CL_{sec} and CL_{re} were inputted in Simcyp as intrinsic clearance values. Intrinsic clearances were calculated using the well-stirred model developed by Rowland *et al.* (1973) [6] (equation 7-8). The fraction unbound in human milk and the total free concentration in human milk were calculated using the Atkinson & Begg equations mentioned above (Equations 3-5).

$$\text{Intrinsic } CL_{sec} = \frac{CL_{sec} \cdot Q}{f_{u_p} (Q - CL_{sec})} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Intrinsic } CL_{re} = \frac{CL_{sec} \cdot Q}{f_{u_{milk, total}} (Q - CL_{sec})} \quad (8)$$

Where Q is the breast tissue blood flow (~3.2% of cardiac output); f_{u_p} fraction unbound in plasma; $f_{u_{milk, total}}$ 'total' free fraction in human milk taking protein and lipid binding into account.

B. Perfusion-limited model

The perfusion-limited lactation model is based on a prediction of the M/P ratio [5]. The module uses a combination of the Fleishaker [2] and Atkinson & Begg [3] models to predict M/P ratio (Equation 9). Alternatively, it is possible to manually set the M/P ratio or to use a user-defined script. The model assumes that there is only transfer of unbound and unionized drugs to milk, then the amount excreted depends on the milk composition, physicochemical properties of the drug.

$$\frac{M}{P} = \frac{f_{u_{plasma}} \cdot f_{u_{plasma}}^{unionized}}{f_{u_{milk}}^{unionized}} \cdot \frac{1}{f_{u_{milk,total}} \cdot \left(\frac{S}{W}\right)} \quad (9)$$

Where $f_{u_{plasma}}$ is unbound fraction of the drug in the plasma predicted within the simulator; the $f_{u_{milk,total}}$ is the unbound fraction of the drug in the milk; S/W is the ratio of drug partitioning between skimmed and whole milk.

Lactation PBPK models were developed for amoxicillin, caffeine and valproic acid in the Simcyp simulator. For amoxicillin and caffeine, the permeability-limited model was used and for valproic acid the model was developed using the perfusion-limited model.

Following adequate agreement between the predictions and the observed clinical data for the reference models, lactation PBPK models were established using the built-in Simcyp lactation modules. A virtual population was created with females aged from 30 to 30.3 years old ($n=1000$). For each simulation, the administration protocol was adapted to the clinical study designs reported in literature. The average (5th-95th percentile) concentration profiles in plasma and human milk were simulated. For calculating the M/P ratio, as well as the exposure, a simulation at steady state with a relatively high common dosing regimen was selected for each compound.

2.2.2. Lactation PBPK model using PK-SIM and MoBi

PK-Sim and MoBi (Open Systems Pharmacology) are an open-source platform that has been extensively used to build PBPK models for different applications. The major benefit of the Open Systems Pharmacology suite is the flexibility to adapt the PBPK model structure in MoBi. The workflow followed in this project is based on the tutorial on how to extend a model to a special population in pregnancy according to Dallmann *et al.* (2018) [7]. They also applied this to simulate the concentration of amoxicillin in the plasma of pregnant and postpartum women [8]. In the Dallmann publication, the physiology was adapted to take the changes in postpartum physiology into account, but the concentration in human milk was not simulated. In a recent publication, the plasma and milk concentrations of ondansetron were simulated by Job *et al.* (2021) [9]. They used a permeability-limited structural model, although they assumed that the permeability to and from human milk was equal and that the partitioning was instantaneous.

Figure 3 Model structure for the lactation module in PK-Sim and MoBi

Lactation PBPK models were developed for the following 10 compounds in PK Sim and Mobi, Open Systems Pharmacology, v9.1: amoxicillin, caffeine, cetirizine, levetiracetam, metformin, nevirapine, sertraline,

tenofovir, valproic acid, zidovudine.

The reference PBPK model was exported to MoBi, where the spatial structure was adapted to represent a postpartum woman. The spatial structure contains a breast compartment, including a subcompartment for the human milk (Figure 3). Human milk (volume = 0.5 L) was directly connected to the plasma compartment, to represent the structure of the empirical model developed by Koshimichi *et al.* (2011) [4]. The transfer to milk, and from human milk were specified in the passive transport building block using Equation 10 and 11. The total free fraction in milk was based on Equations 3-5 from Atkinson and Begg (1990) [3]. The secretion and reuptake clearance values were estimated based on the equations from Koshimichi *et al.* (2001) [4]. It was assumed that metabolizing routes were not present in the human milk. The concentration-time profile for human milk and plasma were simulated and the simulation was saved as *pkml* file.

$$\frac{dN_{milk}}{dt} = C_{plasma} * fu_{plasma} * Cl_{sec} \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{dN_{plasma}}{dt} = C_{milk} * fu_{milk,total} * Cl_{re} \quad (11)$$

In PK Sim, a population was created (n=1000, age=30.2-30.3 years) from the postpartum population by Job *et al.* (2021) to represent the physiological changes in women at three months postpartum [9]. The simulation created in MoBi was then imported for a population simulation. The administration schedule was adapted to the relevant study designs as reported in literature. The average (5th-95th percentile) concentration in plasma and human milk were simulated. For calculating the M/P ratio, as well as the infant dose, a simulation at steady-state with a relatively high common dosing regimen (~worst case scenario) was selected for each compound. A step-by-step manual on how to build a lactation PBPK model in PK Sim and MoBi, Open Systems Pharmacology, as well as the required spatial structure and passive transports are available upon request.

2.3 Infant dose calculation

A simulation at steady-state with a relatively high common dosing regimen (~worst case scenario) was selected to calculate the infant dose via breastfeeding. For this deliverable, we only investigated the exposure at three months postpartum, but a comparable approach can be applied to any postpartum age. The maximum concentration in human milk ($C_{max, milk}$) was obtained from the simulation. The average concentration in human milk ($C_{ave, milk}$) was calculated by dividing the AUC by the dosing interval. The daily human milk intake in infants at this postpartum time interval was assumed to be 150 mL/kg body weight [10]. The daily infant dosage received via breastfeeding after maternal medicine use was calculated using the average, as well as the maximum concentration in human milk (Equation 12). Similarly, the relative infant dose (RID) was calculated using the average, as well as the maximal infant daily dosage in comparison to the daily maternal dosage (Equation 13). In Simcyp, the maternal weight was assumed to be the average weight of the maternal population (30 to 30.3 years old), 65.78 kg. In PK Sim, the maternal weight was assumed to be 60.3 kg, representing the average 3 months postpartum individual from the population by Job *et al.* (2021) [9]. In addition, if the medicine is also used in children, the infant daily dosage via breastfeeding can also be compared to the recommended dose prescribed and administered to infants at the same age.

$$Daily\ infant\ dosage = C_{milk} * 150\ mL/kg/day \quad (12)$$

$$Relative\ infant\ dose\ (RID, \%) = \frac{Daily\ infant\ dosage}{Daily\ maternal\ dosage} * 100\ \% \quad (13)$$

3. Results

PBPK models were developed for 10 medicines in PK-Sim/MoBi and for 3 in Simcyp. Details about the model development and evaluation of the predictive performance are described in medicine-specific reports (available upon request).

3.1 Reference PBPK model

Evaluation of the predictive performance showed that the reference PBPK models were able to capture the pharmacokinetic behavior of the medicines in healthy volunteers and/or patients. Plots showing relative predicted/observed ratios for AUC and C_{max} are shown in Figures 4-12. The plots distinguish between results obtained with ‘building’ versus ‘verification’ data sets, as well as results obtained in both software platforms. Additional details about the reference models can be found in the medicine-specific reports.

Figure 4: Observed/predicted ratios for amoxicillin AUC and C_{max} values. Dashed lines represent 2-fold prediction bias.

Figure 5: Observed/predicted ratios for caffeine AUC and Cmax values. Dashed lines represent 2-fold prediction bias.

Figure 6: Observed/predicted ratios for cetirizine AUC and Cmax values. Dashed lines represent 2-fold prediction bias.

Figure 7: Observed/predicted ratios for levetiracetam AUC and Cmax values. Dashed lines represent 2-fold prediction bias.

Figure 8: Observed/predicted ratios for metformin AUC and Cmax values. Dashed lines represent 2-fold prediction bias.

Figure 9: Observed/predicted ratios for Nevirapine AUC and Cmax values. Dashed lines represent 2-fold prediction bias.

Figure 10: Observed/predicted ratios for sertraline and N-desmethyl-sertraline AUC and Cmax values. Dashed lines represent 2-fold prediction bias.

Figure 11: Observed/predicted ratios for tenofovir AUC and Cmax values. Dashed lines represent 2-fold prediction bias.

Figure 12: Observed/predicted ratios for valproic acid AUC and Cmax values. Dashed lines represent 2-fold prediction bias.

Figure 13: Observed/predicted ratios for zidovudine AUC and Cmax values. Dashed lines represent 2-fold prediction bias.

3.2 Lactation PBPK models

The reference PBPK models were extended to lactation PBPK models for all 10 compounds. The calculated M/P ratios are shown in Table 1.

Lactation PBPK model for Amoxicillin

A representative simulation for amoxicillin is given in Figure 14. The PBPK model was able to predict the human milk concentrations of amoxicillin, with all datapoints within the 5th -95th percentile of the population prediction in both software programs. A dosing regimen of 1000 mg PO three times daily was applied to calculate milk transfer and infant dose.

Figure 14: Predicted concentration time profiles for maternal plasma and milk amoxicillin concentrations as obtained in Simcyp and PK-Sim. Points represent observed data obtained from Kafetzis et al. (1981) after oral administration of 1000 mg.

Lactation PBPK model for caffeine:

A representative simulation for caffeine is given in Figure 15. The PBPK model was able to predict the human milk concentrations of caffeine, with most datapoints within the 5th -95th percentile of the population prediction in both software programs. A single dose regimen of 100 mg PO was then assumed to calculate milk transfer and infant dose.

Figure 15: Predicted concentration time profiles for maternal plasma and milk caffeine concentrations as obtained in Simcyp and PK-Sim. Points represent observed data obtained from Tyrala et al. (1978) after oral administration of 300 mg.

Lactation PBPK model for Cetirizine

A representative simulation for cetirizine is given in Figure 16. The PBPK model results in an overprediction of the human milk concentrations, although the observed data is still within the 5th -95th percentile of the population prediction in the software used. A dosing regimen of 10 mg PO daily was then assumed to calculate milk transfer and infant dose.

Figure 16: Predicted concentration time profiles for maternal plasma and milk cetirizine concentrations as obtained in PK-Sim. Points represent observed data obtained from Wilkerson et al. (2020) after oral administration of 10 mg.

Lactation PBPK model for Levetiracetam

A representative simulation for levetiracetam is given in Figure 17. The PBPK model was able to predict the human milk concentrations of levetiracetam, with most datapoints within the 5th -95th percentile of the population prediction in the software used. A dosing regimen of 1500 mg PO twice daily was then assumed to calculate milk transfer and infant dose.

Figure 17: Predicted concentration time profiles for maternal plasma and milk levetiracetam concentrations as obtained in PK-Sim. Points represent observed data obtained from Johannessen et al. (2005) and Tomson et al. (2007) after oral administration of 1500 mg twice daily.

Lactation PBPK model for Metformin

A representative simulation for metformin is given in Figure 18. The PBPK model was able to predict the human milk concentrations of metformin, with most datapoints within the 5th -95th percentile of the population prediction in the software used. A dosing regimen of 500 mg PO twice daily was then assumed to calculate milk transfer and infant dose.

Figure 18: Predicted concentration time profiles for maternal plasma and milk metformin concentrations as obtained in PK-Sim. Points represent observed data obtained from Briggs et al. (2005), Gardiner et al. (2003) and Zhang et al. (2002) after oral administration of 500 mg twice daily.

For the metformin simulations above, the observed data is from a twice daily regimen and the representative simulation is three times daily regimen. This discrepancy will be resolved in a further iteration of the metformin model.

Lactation PBPK model for Nevirapine

A representative simulation for nevirapine is given in Figure 19. The PBPK model results in an overprediction of the human milk concentrations, although the observed data is still within the 5th -95th percentile of the

population prediction in the software used. A dosing regimen of PO 200 mg twice daily was then assumed to calculate milk transfer and infant dose.

Figure 19: Predicted concentration time profiles for maternal plasma and milk nevirapine concentrations as obtained in PK-Sim. Points represent observed data obtained from Giuliono et al. (2007), Mirochnick et al. (2009), Olagunju et al. (2015/2016), Palombi et al. (2012), Shapiro et al. (2005/2013) and Bennetto-Hood et al. (2007) after oral administration of 200 mg twice daily.

Lactation PBPK model for Sertraline

A representative simulation for sertraline is given in Figure 20. The PBPK model was able to predict the human milk concentrations of sertraline (but not of the metabolite), with most datapoints within the 5th -95th percentile of the population prediction in the software used. A dosing regimen of 50 PO mg daily was then assumed to calculate milk transfer and infant dose.

Figure 20: Predicted concentration time profiles for maternal plasma and milk sertraline concentrations as obtained in PK-Sim. Points represent observed data obtained from Dodd et al. (2000), Pogliani et al. (2019), Salazar et al. (2016), Schoretsanitis et al. (2019), Weisskopf et al. (2017), Weissman et al. (2004), Wisner et al. (1998) and Kristensen et al. (1998) after oral administration of 50 mg twice daily.

Lactation PBPK model for Tenofovir

A representative simulation for tenofovir is given in Figure 21. The PBPK model results in an overprediction of the human milk concentrations, although the observed data is still within the 5th -95th percentile of the population prediction in the software used. A dosing regimen of 300 mg PO daily was then assumed to calculate milk transfer and infant dose.

Figure 21: Predicted concentration time profiles for maternal plasma and milk tenofovir concentrations as obtained in PK-Sim. Points represent observed data obtained from Erturk et al. (2018), Mugwanya et al. (2016), Palombi et al. (2016) and Waitt et al. (2017/2018) after oral administration of 300 mg daily.

Lactation PBPK model for Valproic acid

A representative simulation for valproic acid is given in Figure 21. The PBPK model was able to predict the human milk concentrations of valproic acid, with most datapoints within the 5th -95th percentile of the population prediction in both software programs. A dosing regimen of 2100 mg PO daily was then assumed to calculate milk transfer and infant dose.

Figure 22: Predicted concentration time profiles for maternal plasma and milk valproic acid concentrations as obtained in Simcyp and PK-Sim. Points represent observed data obtained from Vonunruh et al. (1984) after oral administration of 2100 mg daily.

Lactation PBPK model for Zidovudine

A representative simulation for zidovudine is given in Figure 23. The PBPK model was able to predict the human milk concentrations of zidovudine, with most datapoints within the 5th -95th percentile of the population prediction in both software. A dosing regimen of 300 PO mg twice daily was then assumed to calculate milk transfer and infant dose.

Figure 23: Predicted concentration time profiles for maternal plasma and milk zidovudine concentrations as obtained in PK-Sim. Points represent observed data obtained from Corbett et al. (2014), Giuliano et al. (2007), Mirochnick et al. (2009), Palombi et al. (2012) and Shapiro et al. (2005) after oral administration of 300 mg twice daily.

Table 1 Predicted milk-to-plasma (M/P) ratio for 10 medicines. M/P ratios were calculated based on AUC values.

Medicine	Simcyp	PK Sim
Amoxicillin	0.17	0.14
Caffeine	1.44	0.91
Cetirizine	/	1.17
Levetiracetam	/	1.07
Metformin	/	0.15
Nevirapine	/	2.59
Sertraline	/	1.48
Tenofovir	/	1.09
Valproic acid	0.03	0.03
Zidovudine	/	1.00

3.3 Infant dose calculation

The infant dose was calculated based on the simulated concentration-time profiles in human milk at steady-state. Table 2 shows the daily infant dose (mg/kg/day) and relative infant dose (RID, %) that the child receives via breastfeeding during maternal pharmacotherapy at steady state.

Table 2 Daily infant dosage (DID) and relative infant dose (RID) values for 10 medicines.

Medicine	Simcyp		PK Sim	
	Average (mg/kg/day)	Maximal (mg/kg/day)	Average (mg/kg/day)	Maximal (mg/kg/day)
Amoxicillin	0.18 (0.39%)	0.28 (0.62%)	0.11 (0.22%)	0.18 (0.36 %)
Caffeine	0.48 (10.6%)	0.68 (15.1%)	0.39 (7.8 %)	0.48 (9.7 %)
Cetirizine*	/	/	0.02 (12 %)	0.05 (27 %)
Levetiracetam	/	/	5.85 (12 %)	7.59 (15 %)
Metformin	/	/	0.01 (0.07 %)	0.02 (0.12 %)
Nevirapine*	/	/	2.29 (34 %)	2.59 (39 %)
Sertraline	/	/	0.005 (0.58 %)	0.01 (0.72 %)
Tenofovir*	/	/	0.02 (0.44 %)	0.03 (0.63 %)
Valproic acid	0.37 (1.09%)	0.68 (2.02%)	0.60 (1.7 %)	0.94 (2.7 %)
Zidovudine	/	/	0.04 (0.38 %)	0.11 (1.1 %)

Note: Daily infant dosage (DID) in mg/kg/day (relative infant dose (RID) as percentage)

4. Discussion

For the purpose of this study, 10 model medicines were selected based on: (i) availability of clinical data in lactating and non-lactating populations, as needed for model verification purposes; (ii) physicochemical diversity across a range of small molecules with different elimination mechanisms and pathways (hepatic and renal). The purpose of this work was to retrospectively evaluate the predictive performance of newly developed lactation PBPK models by comparing the model-based predictions of the plasma concentration time profiles for the 10 model medicines with clinical observations.

In both software platforms (PK-Sim and Simcyp), the reference models adequately (i.e. < 2-fold bias) predict the pharmacokinetic profiles of the evaluated model medicines. For the PK-Sim platform, the lactation PBPK models were able to predict the pharmacokinetic profile in human milk adequately (without estimation or fitting of parameters for lactation) for 7 of the 10 medicines: amoxicillin, caffeine, levetiracetam, metformin, sertraline (but not N-desmethylsertraline), valproic acid and zidovudine. For cetirizine, nevirapine and tenofovir, although the 5th-95th percentile of the population simulation did include most of the observed datapoints, it is clear by visual inspection that there is an *over*prediction of the human milk concentration (i.e. the observed milk concentrations are lower). At the same time, from a safety perspective, it is reassuring that no *under*predictions for any of the compounds were obtained. With the Simcyp software, the lactation PBPK models were able to predict the pharmacokinetic profile in human milk for caffeine and valproic acid. For amoxicillin, the model somewhat *over*predicted the (initial) milk profile when compared with the observed data, although the AUC values were comparable, thus enabling calculation of the infant dose.

It is the first time that lactation PBPK models are developed according to the same framework for a total of 10 model medicines, making this result an important milestone in this field. Nevertheless, these models represent

a starting point for further improvements and refinements. The following approaches can be used to improve the predictive performance of these models:

- Parameter estimation in the lactation PBPK models is likely to further improve the simulations of the lactation PBPK models. However, this requires availability of (high-quality) clinical data for training and verification, often not (yet) available. Information regarding the dosing regimen, postpartum period and time of sampling is often incomplete in literature.
- The predictions will likely be improved using permeability coefficients generated in an *in vitro* model for the blood milk barrier, especially when active transport is involved. The development and application of such an *in vitro* model is one of the aims of ConcePTION work package 3. Furthermore, this work package also generates *in vivo* data in the minipig, which are expected to reveal additional mechanistic insights.
- Future improvements could include a more mechanistic model in terms of breastfeeding behaviour or human milk composition changes (e.g. pH and lipids) and postpartum period. Presently, a relatively 'basic' PBPK framework was developed, and the focus was on 3 months postpartum. However, the same approach can easily be applied to other postpartum periods. In this context, it should be noted that breastfeeding infants of 2-3 weeks of age are at highest risk in terms of medicine exposure. Indeed, while milk intake is reaching high levels, maturation of elimination pathways is only starting [11].

Importantly, if the concentration in human milk is not accurately predicted (i.e. presently the milk concentrations of cetirizine, nevirapine, tenofovir are *over*predicted), the infant exposure should be interpreted with caution. Furthermore, whether the infant will develop any (toxic) effect from the medicine not only depends on the dose received via breastfeeding, but also on the absorption after oral ingestion. One of the ongoing goals of ConcePTION WP3 is to translate the reference models also to an infant population. In this way, the daily infant dosage via breastfeeding could be used as dosing regimen for a paediatric PBPK model. This would allow to predict infant systemic exposure based on absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion in the infant, taking ontogeny into account. At best, this should be optimized by integrating further information by the specific physiological aspects of the lactating infant. The collection of this physiological information is another ongoing effort of WP3.

The workflow developed here can be applied to predict human milk concentrations of any small molecule medicine. A potential criticism of this PBPK-based method is the complexity of the underlying models, especially when clinical data are available. In our view, this is unjustified, unless rich data sets provide maternal systemic exposure, average concentration in milk and infant systemic exposure. For the sake of clarity, isolated concentrations at arbitrary times after dose don't fall in this category. Indeed, most datasets in this specific 'lactating' population would not even allow identification of simple compartmental models. Instead, borrowing strength (prior knowledge) from physiology and pharmacology allows us researchers to make dose-exposure predictions, even without the availability of any clinical data. That said, ConcePTION work package 4 will generate clinical data for some of the selected model medicines included in this project (metformin, levocetirizine, amoxicillin, venlafaxine).

5. Conclusion

In summary, the lactation PBPK models resulted in adequate predictions of maternal plasma and milk concentration time profiles for 7 medicines, while an overprediction of the concentration time profiles was found for 3 medicines. What is important from a safety perspective, is that none of the models resulted in an underprediction of the milk levels for the given maternal dosing regimen. Comparable results were obtained in both software platforms (PK-Sim and Simcyp). The workflow for PBPK model development and evaluation can be used to simulate the human milk concentration, and calculate predicted infant doses for virtually any (small molecule) medicine. In addition, these models will represent starting points for PBPK models describing PK of biologicals (such as monoclonal antibodies).

The interpretation of these metrics in lieu of clinical policies must be made by domain experts, having been informed about exposure ranges to be expected in all relevant age cohorts.

Furthermore, the ongoing development and application of neonatal and infant PBPK models will allow to translate the infant dose levels predicted by the presently developed lactation PBPK models into infant/neonate systemic exposure. The availability of already existing infant/neonate PBPK models describing PK after ‘direct’ dosing in these populations will be an important advantage. However, modification of these neonate/infant PBPK models will be needed to reflect the impact of ‘administration’ of these maternal medicines via breastmilk (instead of paediatric formulations). Data collection regarding neonatal (physiological) parameters specific to breastfed neonates/infants is currently ongoing as part of the ConcePTION WP3 efforts.

Another step in the refinement of the presently developed lactation models will include the implementation of experimentally determined permeability data for the blood milk barrier. These data are currently being generated with a newly developed *in vitro* model based on human mammary epithelial cells (also as part of ConcePTION WP3). In addition, non-clinical *in vitro* as well as *in vivo* data are being generated in the Göttingen Minipig with some of the model medicines selected for this project. These results are also expected to further strengthen the predictive performance of the human PBPK models.

The generic application potential of the developed lactation PBPK models can be further demonstrated by evaluating additional model medicines, including different therapeutic modalities (e.g. biologicals).

6. References

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